

Employing YouTube Videos to Educate Kindergarten Children in Some Etiquette Arts

Randa El - Deeb,

Kindergarten Department - Faculty of Education - Tanta University -
Gharbia - Tanta, Egypt

Nourhan Nasr Hanafy

Kindergarten Department - Faculty of Education - Kafrel-Sheikh University -
Kafr el-Sheikh, Egypt

Abstract

The research problem was represented in the following main question:

What is the effect of using YouTube videos to develop the arts of etiquette for kindergarten children?

From this main question, the following sub-questions branched out:

- 1- What are the different types of etiquette arts that should be developed among kindergarten children?
- 2- What is the digital content needed to develop some etiquette arts among kindergarten children?
- 3- What is the effect of YouTube video sessions used in developing etiquette arts among kindergarten children?

The research aimed to identify the effect of using some YouTube videos to develop etiquette arts for kindergarten children.

A list of etiquette arts for kindergarten children has been prepared, the experimental treatment material, which is represented in the proposed YouTube videos, illustrated etiquette arts measure for kindergarten children, and a note card for the teacher and mother for the etiquette arts of kindergarten children.

In order to achieve this, the research used the semi-experimental approach, where the sessions were applied to a sample of (30) boys and girls in the age group (5-6) years at the Martyr Mustafa Samir Badawi Official Language School in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, and the illustrated etiquette arts scale was applied. On the children, and the etiquette arts observation card for the mother and the teacher to know the children's performance of the etiquette arts, and the results concluded that the effectiveness of using YouTube videos in developing the art of dealing with others (etiquette) for kindergarten children

Keywords: - Employing, YouTube Videos, Educate, Kindergarten, Children, Etiquette Arts.

Introduction

The interest in the child has increased in the digital age of the twenty-first century, as the means of interaction with children has been linked to the technological development of communications and media. The teacher has ceased to be the only source of knowledge and the school has ceased to be the only educational institution, where other means participate in the educational process, the most important of which is the Internet. Therefore, attention is paid to the Internet as an important and necessary means of presenting children's literature, reading and audio materials in their various forms. The videos and cartoons shown on YouTube are the closest to children's hearts and the most watched. Cartoons are characterized by many positive aspects including: forming the child's habits and giving him many teachings and experiences starting from the appropriate age, so that the child can easily receive all the information.

Research problem

The problem of this research started during our supervision of field work in kindergartens, where we noticed that kindergarten children lack some arts of etiquette. A pilot study was conducted by interviewing (20) kindergarten teachers in Kafrel-Sheikh Governorate. Those teachers were asked whether there was a specific curriculum for Kindergarten teachers through which children can learn the arts of etiquette. And were activities employed in all its different fields to teach kindergarten children etiquette behaviors? kindergarten teachers' answers assured that there was a lack of activities related to teaching the arts of etiquette and there was no specific syllabus or curriculum for Kindergarten teacher to help her guide her children to practice the arts of etiquette, and it was rare to employ artistic, musical, or story activities to teach kindergarten children the arts of etiquette. The child's acquisition of these arts is automatically implicit when other concepts are introduced.

Most of the research works dealt with the study of behavioral etiquette and the variables that control the etiquette behavior of the child. Mitchell (2004) explained that most kindergarten children lack the correct behavior and lack sufficient respect between children and each other and those who are older than them. This was confirmed by Carla's study (2008) stating that the shortcomings that children suffer from in practicing good behaviors with others lead to their weak personality and their feeling of fear and anxiety. Therefore, it can be said that there is an urgent and necessary need to educate kindergarten children on some etiquette and public morals, including proper behavior and good polite manners when dealing with others. This presents them in a civilized and respectful manner, and contributes to developing their information and improving their behaviors and attitudes, using various methods and means, including digital media.

Accordingly, the research problem was formulated in the following main question:

What is the effect of using YouTube videos to develop the arts of etiquette among kindergarten children?

From this main question, the following sub-questions were derived:

- 1- What are the different types of etiquette that should be developed among kindergarten children?
- 2- What is the digital content needed to develop some arts of etiquette for kindergarten children?
- 3- What is the effect of YouTube video sessions used in developing the arts of etiquette among kindergarten children?

Aim:

The current research aims to identify the impact of using some YouTube videos to develop the arts of etiquette among kindergarten children, and the following objectives are derived from this main aim:

- 1- Determining the appropriate etiquette arts for kindergarten children.
- 2- Determining the suitable digital content for the development of some arts of etiquette for kindergarten children.
- 3- Measuring the effect of using YouTube videos on developing the arts of etiquette for kindergarten children.

Importance

The importance of the current research lies in the following:

- 1- This research may raise the awareness of pre-school specialists about the importance of developing the arts of etiquette among kindergarten children.
- 2- Researchers may benefit from the measuring scale provided for etiquette and the observation checklist in this research in studying the development and evaluation of the child.
- 3- This research may be useful for kindergarten children as it provides them with some arts of classy dealing with society, as the child's behaviors can be easily formed at this stage.
- 4- Kindergarten curriculum planners and kindergarten teachers may benefit from the content of the videos presented in this research in providing children with some etiquette for dealing with others.
- 5- This research may benefit parents in providing them with a framework for appropriate digital content via YouTube, in order to provide their children with the basic principles of good behavior, in order to obtain satisfaction and acceptance from society.

Delimitations

1- Spatial and human limits: The research was applied by choosing one of the classes randomly. The sample size was (30) boys and girls from the kindergarten of the Martyr Mustafa Samir Badawi Official Language School in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate in Egypt from the first-level children in the age group from (5-6). Years.

2- Time limits: The experimental treatment and the application of research tools were in the second semester of the academic year 2021/2022.

3- Content limits: The current research was limited to some of the etiquette arts: “greeting etiquette” and “food etiquette”, as these arts are considered among the basics of the child’s daily interaction with others.

Methodology

The current research adopts the quasi-experimental design that depends on the use of a single group. The etiquette pictorial test is used as a pre-test on the experimental group, then the proposed YouTube video sessions are presented to the experimental group, and after finishing the treatment sessions, the etiquette pictorial test is applied again as a post-test.

Theoretical framework and previous studies

Part One: Etiquette

Early childhood is one of the most important stages of a child’s upbringing and education, as what a child acquires in the first years of his/ her life is reflected in his/her behavior. The learned behavior, whether positive or negative, has a significant impact on the formation of his/her future personality. Therefore, it can be said that early childhood is an essential stage in the formation of the child's personality in its physical, psychological, social and mental aspects. Also, the rules and etiquette are of paramount importance for all interactions between people, and cover all aspects of life inside and outside the home, and their acquisition depends on the practices that the child has learned from childhood. Therefore, the upbringing of the child must be developed in these arts; Because these arts are among the important things that will accompany the child in his/her later life and affect his/her personality, which will be appreciated by others.

Thus, etiquette in the current era has become an important requirement and has great importance for all transactions between people and is no longer limited to a specific group or society, but is the product of continuous interactions and long experiences between people and is called the etiquette of life (Al-Ashry and Al-Deeb,2010 : 230).

First: Definition of etiquette

Etiquette is defined as accuracy, public and social taste, the art of dealing with critical situations, self-esteem, respect and appreciation of others, and the formation of good relations with them. It can also be order, the etiquette of formalities, the etiquette of proper behavior, cohabitation, the art of good qualities, or courtesy and the art of pleasing to leave a good impression on its owner (Ali, 2006 ; Barghouth, 2008; Atef, 2016).

Furthermore, Hassan (2009) and Al-Hafni (2013) stated that etiquette is a continuous fabric of tactful rules, behaviors, and regulations that explain how to act in different situations that we face in daily life as well as in our personal lives. Shuli (2020) and

Gallegos, Dziurawiec & Tibury (2018) also added that etiquette is a set of acceptable controls, behaviors, habits and rules related to human behavior in different situations that govern our lives.

Second: Objectives of etiquette learning

There are a number of objectives for teaching etiquette that can be summarized as follows: (Michell, 2008; Wisdom, 2008; Al-Attar, 2010; Daher, 2011 ; Olberding, 2015 ; Huahua, 2017; Ziguu, 2018; and Yaoqi, 2019)

- Guiding children and adults to the most appropriate rules and good civilized behavior expected from them to perform.
- Dealing successfully in social situations, which makes them more respected and accepted by others.
- Feeling of comfort, calm and serenity when dealing with others.
- Persistence and continuity of social relationships for a long period of time, such as friendships.
- Show respect to all people.
- It provides them with life chances.
- Develop the child's self-confidence.
- Strengthening human relations.
- It makes them able to gain the trust of others.
- Communication between civilizations and rapprochement between peoples.
- Reflects a positive or negative view of human behavior.
- Develop the basic personality traits necessary for social life.
- Increase their chances of success in family, school and social life.

Third: The importance of teaching etiquette to children

Children benefit from the art of etiquette in regulating their behavior, expressing mutual respect, building friendship and respect, harmonizing social relations and instilling and strengthening moral qualities. Etiquette has also become an important criterion for measuring the personal morals and social civilization of nations. Thus, teaching children the art of etiquette and good habits can contribute to the formation of a positive image, in addition to its important role in ensuring the social stability of society. Huiling (2019), Cui (2019), Dereshev & Kirk (2017) and Clark (2015) have shown that the art of etiquette is necessary for kindergarten children for the following reasons:

- It teaches the child respect, tolerance and positive values.
- The child learns to respect personal freedoms.
- The child learns the etiquette of asking permission upon request.
- The child learns to speak, listen and behave correctly.
- It makes the child leave his fingerprints everywhere s/he goes.
- Enhancing a sense of trust and loyalty, by building a sense of responsibility and maturity, and appreciating relationships.

- Teaching etiquette in kindergarten forms the basis for all elements of social etiquette in their later lives.

Fourth: Areas of etiquette arts

There are many forms of etiquette that have been dealt with in many previous studies and literature. Fraihat (2005) identified sitting etiquette, greeting etiquette, food etiquette, and conversation etiquette. Abdel-Aal (2006) added the etiquette of appearance, visitation, and speech. Furthermore, Al-Ashry and Al-Deeb (2010) mentioned the etiquette of greeting, speech, use of telephone, visitation, permission, and table.

Al-Attar (2010) also clarified the areas of etiquette in which pre-school children should be educated, represented in the etiquette of greeting, carefully listening to others, the etiquette associated with attending parties, school rules, and respect between friends during musical activities. In addition, Al-Ashry and Nassar (2018) also dealt with the etiquette of speaking and asking permission, the etiquette of visiting, the etiquette of dining and table, and the etiquette of bathroom. Sharaf (2019) tackled the arts of dialogue, clothing, and food. Furthermore, Al-Jayyar (2020) identified the etiquette of holidays and events, the etiquette inside the hall, visiting the patient, dealing with pets, food and hospitality, permission, and playing with friends.

The current research aims to shed light on some arts of etiquette, such as greeting and food etiquette

Greeting Etiquette:

Greeting is the first step in any social interaction, as it allows for positive contact with other people to be established. To say hello, the child should look at the person s/he is talking to, smile and say “Happy day”, “Good morning” or “Peace be upon you”.

Al-Attar (2010) mentioned some of the behaviors that the child practices when greeting others, such as:

- Stand up to greet.
- Smiling in the face of those who greet him, the smile expresses acceptance, welcome and respect, and this gives a positive initial impression.
- Uses appropriate words to greet such as: hello, good morning, good day, good evening.
- Says the appropriate salutation at the end of the interview such as: good bye, farewell and nice to meet you.

Munir (2005: 202) stated that the best way to teach a child moral virtues such as greeting, is to teach it from the early stages of childhood, because of its impact on the stability of character in the child, and the following are some ways to teach the child to greet:

- Teaching the child to greet by setting a good example, by seeing his parents, relatives and those around him/ her greet and salute each other, smile and welcome each other, instilling in him/her these manners since childhood.
- Teaching the child to greet gradually, especially if s/he is shy, or finds it difficult to memorize the words of greetings. This gives him/her a lot of opportunities to learn the formula of greetings, after which s/he will get used to interacting with people and gradually responding to them.
- by repeating salutation to him/her and reminding him/her of the importance of greeting and salutation. Repetition is one of the best ways to teach children new behaviors.

Food Etiquette:

Eating food has etiquette that every person should learn in his/ her life, as it gives an impression to others about the personality of the individual, and shows the extent to which s/he is civilized and sophisticated in society. Several studies such as Al-Ashry and Al-Deeb (2010), Sulaiman (2011), and Gyure et. al, (2014) showed that food etiquette requires some rules and practices as follows:

- Eat gently and politely.
- Don't talk while food is in your mouth.
- Do not make a sound while tasting food or drinking water or juice.
- Do not fill the plate with more food than necessary.
- Do not blow on food.
- Close your mouth while chewing and do not make a sound.
- Don't eat other people's food.
- Do not put your personal items on the dining table.
- Start eating with others.
- Don't point at cutlery while talking.
- Do not eat with cutlery that have fallen to the ground.
- Do not throw the food napkin on the table violently.
- Do not use the towel to clean your face or nose.
- Don't talk on the phone while eating.

The study of Arganini et. al. (2012) emphasized the importance of chewing food well and eating calmly so as not to face health and digestion problems. The child must deal with his/her own plate and tools. We must help the child to behave politely and elegantly while eating his/her food. Each type of food has a way to eat it.

Part Two: YouTube

YouTube is one of the most popular and most widespread digital content networking sites in the world, used by both the old and the young, but this site has become a great attraction for children, due to its technical features that allow them to display knowledge, information and behaviors in an attractive and exciting style. In addition

to the integration and diversity of the elements of the artistic embodiment of its material, the simplicity of its structure, its content, its form and its expressive language, as well as the colorful animated images associated with sound (video), in which the child clearly sees easy expressive methods, which enhances its ability to fascinate and attract children's attention, thanks to its enjoyment of electronic enhancements , since the child from a young age has been fascinated by the moving thing that falls under his/her visual and auditory sense, in addition to the freedom to choose and move from one video to another, as well as the freedom to choose the time to watch, not to mention the ease of use. It only takes a few steps for the child, which becomes easier with frequent use of the site.

First: the concept of YouTube

Abdul Ghafour (2015) defined YouTube as one of the most important tools of the second generation of the Internet as a publishing tool, through which it allows the teacher to provide visual and audio information, implement video projects, and publish it to students via e-mail or social networks, so that they can view it at any time.

Roodt & Peier (2013) also defined it as a popular video-sharing site where users can upload, watch and share videos. and personal videos uploaded by users, and these videos can be viewed by anyone with an internet connection.

Second: the pros and cons of YouTube for children

Danique de Jong (2019) believed that among the positives of YouTube on children's behavior are the following:

- Learning the language through native speakers.
- Learning in a fun and engaging way.
- Learning positive behavior through meaningful stories.

Danique de Jong also added that among the negative aspects of YouTube on children's behavior are the following:

- Kids rely heavily on YouTube
- All videos are public
- You Tube addiction.
- The presence of sexual language depicted in the form of cartoons
- Embodiment of characters that represent dangerous and violent behavior
- Spread of jokes about drug abuse and child sexual abuse
- Direct talk about domestic violence, child pornography and suicide among children
- Cartoon characters that are not purposeful and show negative behaviors that the child takes as an example and imitates

Al-Khayyat (2020) pointed out that there are many negative things that parents face when dealing with the child's use of technology, the most important of which is their fear that the child will spend a lot of time in front of the screen, their poor ability to

organize bedtime, and the child wasting a lot of time in front of the screen, It isolated the child from social interaction with those around him. Besides, there are many advantages for the child to watch YouTube, as s/ he learns new information, enables him/her to search for new information, and introduces the child to the culture of the community and other cultures around him.

Third: The role of parents in protecting children from the dangers of YouTube

Fakhr El-Din (2021) stated that parents have a great role in protecting their children from the dangers of YouTube, including:

- Set a time to watch with the child, and in the event of inappropriate videos, they must be reported and blocked immediately.
- Allow children to watch in the places where the mother or father is, such as the kitchen, and not in children’s own rooms to allow for monitoring.
- Discuss with children the dangers of YouTube, that it is not the best place to spend time, and give them a good reason why YouTube is dangerous.
- Set a specific time for the child to watch YouTube, and make sure that s/he does not exceed it, so as not to become addicted to YouTube.

Ben Miloud (2020) recommended that parents monitor their children and what they are exposed to, especially with child protection programs that can be downloaded and used easily, and if necessary, prevent them from using smart phones. It is desirable to create an entertainment environment away from these means.

Fourth: The importance of using YouTube in teaching and learning

E-learning is an effective way to learn using the Internet, and it is one of the most successful processes that help and contribute to the ease of gaining information, due to its many advantages and different fields. E-learning provides courses and syllabuses to students, allowing them to learn anytime and anywhere, in addition to interacting with them (Mandour, 2013).

Smith (2011) added a number of additional features to YouTube, such as student engagement, whereas displaying a large number of valuable videos leads to attracting students and engaging them in the digital world in order to achieve educational goals. And these videos involve more than one sense in learning, which increases their awareness of the instructional topic.

Bullas (2013) believed that one of the best features of YouTube is the search function. For example, if it is difficult to find a suitable video for the topic of the lesson, you can search for the YouTube channel dedicated to this topic. YouTube also provides related videos feature, which allows the user to explore a selection of videos with similar title or content.

Methodology and Procedures:

First: Methodology

The quasi-experimental method was used for its relevance to the nature of the research. The one group pre-posttest design was used. The study participants were pre-tested, exposed to the treatment then post-tested.

Second: Sample

The research sample was selected from the kindergarten children of the Martyr Mustafa Samir Badawi Official Language School in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate. The sample consisted of (30) boys and girls. The children's age ranged between 5 to 6 years old.

Third: Tools and Materials

The following tools and materials were prepared:

- 1- The Etiquette pictorial test for kindergarten children.
- 2- The experimental treatment material, which is represented in the suggested YouTube videos.

Fourth: The implementation of the experimental sessions

1- After designing “The Etiquette Pictorial Test for Kindergarten Children”, it was presented to a jury panel in the Kindergarten Department for validation. It was modified according to the jurors' suggestions, and it was put in its final form to be used. The pre-application of the research tool was done on a sample of kindergarten children. One of the kindergarten classes of the Martyr Mustafa Samir Badawi Official Language School was chosen to be the sample of this research. This sample is considered representative of the original community. This research sample consisted of (30) children.

2- After the pre-application of the study tool, the YouTube video sessions used in developing children's etiquette were applied to the children of the research group, in the time period from 6/3/2022 to 17/4/2022 in the academic year 2021/2022.

3- After finishing the experimental sessions, the post application of the research tool, represented in the etiquette pictorial test for kindergarten children was carried out on the children of the research group.

Fifth: Results

To verify the validity of the research hypothesis, which states that:

*There is a statistically significant difference at the 0.05 level between the mean scores of the experimental group children in the pre and post-test on the total score of the etiquette pictorial test in favor of the post-test.

The following hypotheses emerged from this main hypothesis:

- 1- There is a statistically significant difference at the 0.05 level between the mean scores of the experimental group children in the pre and post-test on greeting etiquette in favor of the post-test.

2- There is a statistically significant difference at the 0.05 level between the mean scores of the experimental group children in the pre and post-test on food etiquette in favor of the post-test.

To compare between the performance of the experimental group in the pre and post measurements on the etiquette pictorial test, a paired samples t-test was conducted to determine the effect of the used YouTube videos on developing children’ Etiquette and the results were as follows:

Table (1): t- values for the experimental group on the etiquette pictorial test

	Measurement	N	Mean	Difference	Std. Deviation	df	t- Value	Sig.	d	Effect Size
Greeting Etiquette	Pre	30	2.40	1.43	1.43	29	8.08	0.01	1.47	Large
	Post	30	3.83							
Food Etiquette	Pre	30	5.03	3.47	3.47	29	14.25	0.01	2.60	Large
	Post	30	8.50							
Total Score	Pre	30	7.43	4.98	4.98	29	27.11	0.01	4.95	Large
	Post	30	12.33							

The results in table (1) shows that the t-value = 27.11 for the total score of the etiquette pictorial test which indicates that there is a statistically significant difference at the (0.01) level between the pre- and posttest mean scores of the experimental group in favor of the post test. On the basis of this finding, the first main hypothesis was accepted. The effect size was large (d= 4.95). This means that the YouTube videos affected the development of kindergarten children’s Etiquette to a high degree.

Results of the greeting Etiquette in table (1) shows that the t-value =8.08 which is statistically significant at the (0.01) level. This indicates the existence of a significant difference between the mean scores of the children in the pre and post measurements of the greeting etiquette scale in favor of the post measurement. The effect size was large (d=1.47), which indicates that YouTube videos had a significant role in developing the art of greeting etiquette for kindergarten children. On the basis of this finding, the first sub-hypothesis was accepted.

Results of the food Etiquette in table (1) shows that the t-value=14.25 which is statistically significant at the (0.01) level, which indicates the existence of a significant difference between the mean scores of the children in the pre and post

measurements of the food etiquette scale in favor of the post measurement. The effect size was large ($d=2.60$), which indicates that YouTube videos had a significant role in developing the art of food etiquette for kindergarten children. On the basis of this finding, the second sub-hypothesis was accepted.

Research Recommendations

In light of the research results, the following recommendations can be made:

- 1- Reconsidering the value of YouTube videos, and that they are not just for entertainment and fun, and give them the importance they deserve as an important element in raising and educating kindergarten children.
- 2- The necessity of purposefully applying the arts of etiquette in kindergartens, and integrating them into the kindergarten curricula.
- 3- Educating parents about the importance of practicing the arts of etiquette in front of their children, so that it becomes a habit for them and they become a good role model for their children.
- 4- The need to allocate time to watch educational videos in the daily program of kindergarten.

Research Suggestions

In light of the previous research findings and recommendations, we suggest conducting the following future research:

- 1- The effectiveness of using YouTube in developing the creative thinking skills of kindergarten children.
- 2- A proposed media program to qualify female students in early childhood colleges to produce educational media for children.
- 3- Cultural media for kindergartens as reflected in YouTube videos.
- 4- Using YouTube videos to instill behaviors of respectful dealing with patients and the elderly.

References

- Abdel Ghafour, Saeed (2015). “The effect of using some of the suggested educational media via the World Wide Web on the achievement of the ninth grade student in geography in Khan Yunis Governorate”. Unpublished M.A. thesis, Al-Azhar University, Gaza, Palestine.
- Abdel-Al, Jamal Sayed (2006). Your behavior is the title of your personality. *Administrative Development - Egypt*: Vol. 27, No.823, pp. 128-129.
- Al-Ashry, Enas Farouk and Nassar, Hanan Abdel Halim (2018). The effectiveness of a program based on the use of educational scaffolding strategies to improve the etiquette behaviors of a kindergarten child. *Childhood Magazine*, Cairo University. (30).
- Al-Attar, Nelly Mohamed Saad (2010). The role of music activities in educating the kindergarten child in some etiquette behaviors. *Journal of Childhood and Education*, Faculty of Kindergarten, Alexandria University, Vol. 2, No. 5, pp. 157-238.
- Al-Gayar, Salwa Ali (2020). The effect of producing a radio program on developing some etiquette concepts for a sample of pre-school children. *The Egyptian Journal of Media Research*, Cairo University, No. 72.
- Ali, Sawsan Hajj (2006). *Etiquette guide in the business world*. Shuaa Publishing and Science: Aleppo.
- Al-Khayyat, Laila Saud (2020). The use of YouTube and its relationship to changing social values among Kuwaiti children from the point of view of parents. *The Educational Journal*, Kuwait University, Vol. (34), No.134.
- Arganini, C, Saba, A, Comitato, R, et al. (2012). “Gender differences in food choice and dietary intake in modern western societies”. In: Maddock, J (ed.) *Public Health Social and Behavioral Health*. New York: In Tech.
- Atef, Hani (2011). *Etiquette Protocol*, p. 7. Retrieved from
– <http://www.slideshare.net/hanyatef/ss-60982484>
- Barghout, Ali (2008). *Public Relations Diplomacy*. Sultan for Printing and Publishing: Gaza.
- Ben Miloud, Shams Al-Huda and Alawi, Khaled (2020). Social networking sites and their implications for the moral values of a pre-school child: An analytical study of YouTube content provided to children. *Journal of Human Sciences*, University of Mentouri, Constantine, Vol. 21, No.2.
- Bullas, A.J. (2013). *The Facts and Figures on YouTube in infographic*. New York: Pearson education limited.
- Carla, S (2008). Teaching manners to preschool children: Appropriate manners for kids, [article// daycare, suite.com](http://daycare.suite.com).
- Clark, R. M. (2015). *Family Life and school achievement: Why poor Black Children succeed or fail*. University of Chicago Press, p 27.

- Cui, X. (2019). Public Etiquette Education Research in Kindergarten Etiquette Textbook, MA Thesis, Southwest University.
- Daher, Nadine (2011). Etiquette science and fitness. International Academy, Beirut.
- Danique de Jong, (2019). The Advantages and Disadvantages of YouTube. Retrieved from <https://snobmonkey.com/the-advantages-and-disadvantages-of-youtube/>
- Dereshev, D., & Kirk, D. (2017). Form, Function and Etiquette-Potential Users Perspectives on social domestic robots. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction*, Vol. 1 , No.2, 12.
- El Hafni, Nadia (2013). Etiquette and the art of dealing with others. Arab House Library, Cairo.
- El-Ashry, Enas Farouk and El-Deeb, Randa Mostafa (2010). Etiquette of the kindergarten child and its relationship to some variables. *Journal of the College of Education*, Tanta University, p. (41).
- Fakhruddin, Amani (March 2021). The pros and cons of YouTube on children's behavior. Retrieved from <https://www.almrsal.com/post/1033003>
- Freihat, Hikmat Abdel Karim (2005). Teaching the Child Social Etiquette, *Huda al-Islam Journal*, Jordan: Vol. 49, No. 1, pp. 97-103.
- Gallegos, D., Dziurawiec, S., Tilbury, F. (2018). Eating with your mouth shut: family meals and etiquette, TASA Conference 2018, University of Western Australia & Murdoch University.
- Gyure, M. E., Quillin, J. M., Rodriguez, V. M., Markowitz, M. S., Corona, R. A., Borzelleca, J. F., & Bodurtha, J. N. (2014). Parctical Considerations For Implementing Research Recruitment Etiquette. *IRB*, 36 (6), 7.
- Hassan, Afaf Muhammad (2006). The Art of Etiquette. Dar Al-Mustaqbal for Publishing and Distribution: Cairo.
- Huahua, G. (2017). A Study of Etiquette Education for Children and Adolescents from the Perspective of Cognitive Behavior Theory, MA Thesis, Henan Normal University.
- Huiling, J. (2019). A Study on the Moral Educational Function of Chinese Korean Life Etiquette, MA Thesis, Southwest University.
- Mandour, Enas Mohamed (2013). The effect of a training program for graduate students at the College of Education in designing electronic tests according to the proposed quality standards. *Journal of educational and social studies*. Vol.19, No.2, pp. 391-460.
- Michell, M. (2004). The complete idiot’s guide to etiquette. Penguin.
- Michell, M. (2008). Family education behavior etiquette. Retrieved from <http://ifefamilyeducation.com/behavior-etiquette-148460.htm>.

- Mounir, Morsi Muhammad (2005). Islamic Education: Its Origins and Development in Arab Countries, p. 202.
- Olberding, A. (2015). From Corpses to Courtesy: Xunzi's Defense of Etiquette. *The Journal of Value Inquiry*, Vol. 44, No. 1-2, pp.145-159.
- Roodt. S.& Peier. D. (2013). Using YouTube in the Classroom for the Net Generation of Students. University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa, Vol. 10, pp 473-487.
- Sharaf, Iman Abdullah (2019). The Effectiveness of a Dramatic Activities Program in Kindergarten Children's Acquisition of Some Arts of Etiquette, *Childhood Magazine*, Faculty of Early Childhood Education, Cairo University, Vol. 31, No.1, pp. 180-227.
- Shuli, Y. (2020). A Study on the Etiquette Education Thoughts and Modern Values in "The Family Instructions of Yan Family", MA Thesis. Shanghai Normal University.
- Smith, J. (2011): The YouTube Revolution: Engagement, Perception & Identity, Vol.3, No.42, pp.117-221.
- Suleiman, Sanaa Muhammad (2011). The arts of etiquette and classy treatment. Cairo: World of Books, p. 173.
- Wisdom, J. (2008). Dictionary of Etiquette. Retrieved from <http://www.greengonzo.com/dictionary/Equitutte.htm>
- Yaogi, M. (2019). Family etiquette education is the foundation of children's civilized etiquette behavior. *Education Modernization*, (28).
- Zigu, H. (2018). The Cultivation of Middle School Students' Etiquette Quality in Middle School Chinese Teaching. MA Thesis, Jiangxi Science and Technology Normal University.